

SPONTANEOUS DECOMPOSITION OF *o*-DIAZO-*O*-METHOXY- ACETOPHENONE

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o-Diazo-*O*-methoxyacetophenone has been synthesised in crude form. The liquid diazo-ketone decomposes spontaneously with loss of nitrogen and deposition of a solid ketone of the composition $C_9H_8O_2$, characterised by its semicarbazone. The diazo-ketone gives by Arndt-Eistert synthesis *O*-methoxyphenylacetamide. The solid ketone adds bromine and forms a dibromide, $C_9H_8O_2Br_2$. It is inferred that in the formation of solid ketone the radical of diazo-ketone undergoes some rearrangement other than the Wolff rearrangement.

A method for preparing diazo-ketones $R-CO-CH=N\equiv N$ in satisfactory yields from the corresponding acid chloride, $R.CO.Cl$ has been described by Robinson and Bradley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1310). It consists in adding an ethereal solution of the chloride (1 mol.) to ethereal solution of an excess (2.5 mol.) of diazomethane at -10° . Nitrogen is slowly evolved due to the action of hydrochloric acid formed in (i) on the excess of diazomethane.

We used this process and treated *O*-methoxybenzoyl chloride (1 mol.) with diazomethane (2.5 mol.) in ether. After completion of the reaction and evaporation of the solvent at room temperature under reduced pressure *o*-diazo-*O*-methoxyacetophenone (I) was left in crude form as a liquid in an almost quantitative yield.

(I)

The crude diazo-ketone, right from the time of its isolation from the solvent, began to decompose spontaneously and continuously at room temperature, losing a gas in minute bubbles. When the tube containing the liquid ketone was corked, an appreciable pressure was developed in a few minutes due to accumulation of nitrogen. Simultaneously a pale yellow crystalline solid was slowly being deposited. The latter on examination was found to be free from nitrogen. It melted at 104° and gave on analysis results agreeing with the composition $C_9H_8O_2$, which is that of the radical

(II)

The existence of the diazo-ketone (I) in the liquid was proved as follows: By the action of ammonia on the freshly prepared liquid in presence of silver nitrate (catalyst) in dioxane, the Arndt-Eistert synthesis expected of diazo ketones took place (*Ber.*,

1935, 68, 200). An amide (m.p. 131°) was obtained having the composition $C_9H_{11}O_2N$. Hydrolysis of the amide gave an acid identified as *O*-methoxyphenylacetic acid. The amide is therefore *O*-methoxyphenylacetamide (IV) formed, as expected, by the Wolff rearrangement of the radical (II) to the ketene (III) which subsequently adds ammonia to give the amide.

The solid (m.p. 104°) gives a semicarbazone (m.p. 220°) whose analysis gives results corresponding with the composition $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_2$, which is that of the semicarbazone of the ketone $C_9H_9O_2$. It is noteworthy that addition of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate to the crude liquid diazo-ketone gives the same semicarbazone as that of the nitrogen-free solid. Since during the period of semicarbazone formation (one day) nitrogen is evolved, it is inferred that the diazo-ketone turns into nitrogen-free solid and the semicarbazone formed is that of the latter compound.

The observation about the semicarbazone does not give information about the mass and structure of the molecule of the solid beyond the fact that one $C_9H_9O_2$ unit reacts with one molecule of semicarbazide.

Thermal decomposition of diazo-ketones in amyl ether at temperatures exceeding 110° was studied by Schroeter (*Ber.*, 1916, 49, 2743) who observed quantitative evolution of nitrogen and formation of oily residues in which neither the dimers of ketenes nor the isomeric cyclobutane diones could be identified. Grundmann (*Annalen*, 1938, 536, 29) observed thermal non-catalysed decomposition of ω -diazoacetophenone and showed that the decomposition product was *cis*-1:2:3-tribenzoylcyclopropane (V)

The decomposition under similar conditions of the diazo-ketone, prepared from phenylacetyl chloride, catalysed by cupric oxide, affords, however, $\alpha\beta$ -diphenylacetylene. The decomposition of ω -diazo-*O*-methoxyacetophenone (I) is non-catalysed and spontaneous, and therefore differs somewhat from cases of decomposition cited above. Whether [the radical formed from a molecule of a diazo-ketone after loss of nitrogen, polymerised to a cyclopropane or ethylenic compound, could be ascertained from the knowledge about the molecular weight of the product of polymerisation. In the case of the solid (m.p. 104°) the value of the molecular weight found by cryoscopic method in benzene came to be 140 ($C_9H_9O_2$, M.W. = 148).

The solid (m.p. 104°) is neutral in reactions and can be crystallised from boiling water unchanged. In contact with aqueous ferric chloride it develops a dark violet colour after prolonged standing. Its solution in carbon tetrachloride absorbs bromine very slowly at 0° in diffused daylight. A small proportion of hydrobromic acid gas is also evolved. The solid bromo compound left after removal of the solvent and after crystallisation melted at 147° . The result of its analysis corresponds with the composition $C_9H_8O_2Br_2$. Neither the cyclopropane nor the ethylenic structure is therefore admissible for the solid.

The observations so far made indicate that the radical (II) undergoes some rearrangement other than the Wolff rearrangement to produce a stable molecule capable of accepting two atoms of bromine slowly. The nature of this rearrangement will become clear in the light of further work we are doing on the compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

*ω -Diazo-*o*-methoxyacetophenone.*—*O*-Methoxybenzoyl chloride (b.p. $180^\circ/120$ mm., 6.5 g., 1 mol.), dissolved in dry ether, was slowly added to an ethereal solution of diazomethane, prepared from 18.6 g. of nitrosomethylurea (the solution contained about 4 g., 2.5 mol. of gaseous diazomethane). The temperature was maintained at -10° and the addition spread over a period of 1 hour. Nitrogen was slowly evolved. The reaction mixture was kept at 0° for 4 hours and then at room temperature overnight. The solvent was then removed by evaporation under reduced pressure at room temperature. The crude diazo-ketone weighed 6.8 g.

Formation of the Decomposition Product.—The crude diazo-ketone began to decompose spontaneously with loss of nitrogen and deposition of a solid. From 3 g. of the diazo-ketone 1.5 g. of the solid were collected during 2 days. The rate of decomposition fell with lapse of time. The pale yellow crystalline deposit is soluble in usual organic solvents and separates from hot dilute alcohol in pale yellow short prisms, m.p. 104° . [Found: C, 72.5; H, 4.7; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 140. $C_9H_8O_2$ requires C, 72.9; H, 5.4 per cent. M. W., 148].

The *semicarbazone* of the solid compound (m.p. 104°) crystallises from hot dilute alcohol in small needles, m.p. 220° . (Found: N, 21.2. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_2$ requires N, 20.5 per cent).

Addition of semicarbazide [hydrochloride and sodium acetate to the crude liquid diazo-ketone yielded a semicarbazone after standing for 1 day. Crystallised from alcohol it melted at 220° and when mixed with the semicarbazone of the solid produced no depression in its melting point.

The Bromine Addition Product of the Solid.—The solid (m.p. 104° , 0.3 g.) was dissolved in carbon tetrachloride (4 c.c.) and to the solution cooled by ice, bromine dissolved in the same solvent was added until red colour persisted. Hydrobromic acid was evolved in small proportion. The residue left after evaporation of the solvent at room temperature is a yellow solid which crystallises from alcohol in clustering needles, m.p. 147° , yield 0.3 g. (Found: Br, 53.1. $C_9H_8O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 52.0 per cent).

**O*-Methoxyphenylacetamide.*—The freshly prepared diazo-ketone (3 g.) was dissolved in dioxane (20 c.c.) and 30% solution of ammonia (20 c.c.) and 10% solution of silver

nitrate (3 c.c.) were added. The mixture was left overnight and then refluxed on a water-bath for 4 hours. The precipitated silver oxide was filtered and the filtrate evaporated on the water-bath when a white solid mixed with black silver residue was left. The former was extracted with ether and after removal of the solvent the crude amide weighed 1.5 g. and it was purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol. The pure amide melts at 131° . (Found: N, 9.3. $C_9H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 8.5 per cent).

The amide was heated with aqueous caustic potash until no more ammonia evolved. On cooling and acidifying the clear solution an oily emulsion was obtained from which on standing a crystalline solid acid separated. It crystallises from hot water in small needles, m. p. 124° . *O*-Methoxyphenylacetic acid melts at 124° . (Found: Equiv., 165.0. $C_9H_{10}O_2$ requires equiv., 166.0).

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